

The management, reuse and reconstruction of solid waste.

University innovation

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Abstract:

The document presented describes the experience of a group of university students enrolled in the Sustainable Development course, which is part of the academic programme of a higher education institution. These students developed a project to address environmental sustainability issues related to solid waste. The methodology implemented to achieve the proposed goal was based on Project-Based Learning (PBL) and the Technology Project (Proy. Tec.) methodology adapted to first-semester students. This pedagogical approach is implemented to foster a creative, innovative spirit in the design and construction of devices that contribute to the efficient management of solid waste. To illustrate the above, a project carried out by a group of students is attached. Overall, the outcome was positive, as the students demonstrated a high level of commitment by proposing an innovative idea that would practically address a social need and contribute to environmental protection and human well-being.

Keywords: human wellbeing, innovation, reconstruction, reuse, solid waste management.

1 INTRODUCTION

Caring for the environment is, today, a matter of extreme urgency. The planet is at a point of no return; despite international agreements, solid waste generation continues to rise alongside population growth. According to analyses by the United Nations (UN), various international organisations, researchers, and ecosystem advocacy groups, by 2050, there will be so much solid waste that it will seriously impact the living environment of all species on the planet.

Therefore, it is not enough to raise social awareness of the importance of caring for, protecting, and preserving the environment; it is imperative to give top priority to implementing educational programmes (at all levels), accompanied by concrete actions that address this problem. In this regard, universities have integrated subjects that meet this

objective into their academic programmes. Although they are sometimes not given the importance they deserve, these initiatives remain of great significance.

In this context, the manuscript aims to disseminate the activities derived from the Sustainable Development course, taught to Mechatronics students at a Higher Education Institution (HEI) located in southern Tamaulipas, Mexico. These activities take place during the first semester of the academic year and involve carrying out projects that generate a significant social impact. As a result, students developed an interest in designing and manufacturing objects from solid waste, with the aim of extending their useful life and protecting the environment. The following section will explain this in greater detail.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Backgrounds.

Various studies have determined the importance of solid waste management (SWM) in higher education institutions (HEIs). In this regard, the work carried out by Uruce et al. (2024) aimed to assess the level of knowledge and practices related to solid waste management among university students in a region of Peru, which involved a non-experimental, quantitative, correlational, and prospective study, selecting a sample of 228 students. To collect data, the authors applied two nationally validated questionnaires, evaluating practice using Cronbach's alpha (0.823) and knowledge using the Kuder-Richardson formula (0.755). The results showed a prevalence of the 20-24 age group (86%) and females (89%). Regarding knowledge of SWM, the results were mixed: while the overall percentage of correct answers (62.3%) indicated an average level of understanding, students varied in their comprehension of certain topics. The highest performance was on the question about solid waste recovery ($\bar{X} = 0.92$; $SD = 0.25$), while the lowest was on the question about solid waste generation. Regarding waste management practices, 71.5% were carried out satisfactorily. Therefore, it is clear that greater knowledge leads to improved application of these practices.

In another documentary-based study, based on a search of the National Registry of Higher Education Options (RENOES) and data analysis using the R programming language (R Core Team, 2023), conducted at the University of Veracruz, Mexico, Olivo et al. (2024) have expressed concern about the absence of subjects related to GRS in higher education programmes at the national level. This situation has been identified as a significant deficit in addressing the problem, underscoring the crucial importance of integrating it into academic curricula. In addition, there was a marked tendency to offer these subjects as electives rather than integrating them as compulsory components of the educational programme, particularly at the postgraduate level. The authors thus highlight the urgent need to modernise and expand the range of university educational programmes related to the national problem of solid waste. This change is crucial for training competent professionals and researchers who are prepared to face the challenges ahead.

The study by Girone et al. (2024) examined the implementation of solid waste management strategies through the circular economy in the municipality of Ulcumayo, Peru, and employed a mixed-methods, descriptive, cross-sectional design. To collect data, observation guides were used, questionnaires were administered, and interviews were conducted to analyse the current state of waste management in the community. The study sample was carefully selected from a population subgroup within the district of Ulcumayo. The findings revealed a significant deficit in knowledge about the circular economy and solid waste management. On the other hand, participants expressed a high degree of acceptance and willingness to adopt initiatives related to the circular economy and proper solid waste management. Therefore, the study highlighted the importance of implementing sustainable strategies that promote socioeconomic development and improve environmental quality.

2.2 Economic prosperity and solid waste generation

Population growth and industrial development have led to a significant increase in waste generation, causing a range of environmental and public health problems, including the proliferation of harmful wildlife and contamination of water, soil, and air. Urban development and population growth have generated significant demand for natural

resources, leading to overexploitation and a decline in their availability. This has given rise to two of the most pressing environmental problems of the 21st century: excessive waste generation and environmental pollution (Sánchez and Alarcón, 2024).

On the other hand, Choquehuanca et al. (2024) emphasise that inefficient solid waste management is one of the main environmental and public health challenges associated with urbanisation. This situation leads to increased waste generation. In response to this situation, international organisations such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the World Bank (WB) have noted that much of the waste generated is poorly managed, posing a threat to the environment and human health.

For example, in Latin America, waste generation is high. The region draws attention due to daily waste volumes, rising informal landfills, waste burning, and poor disposal practices (UN, 2026). In Mexico, the capital's largest landfill, Bordo Poniente, closed in 2011. About 70 million tonnes of waste remain buried there. It is urgent to develop innovative solutions to reduce, manage, and reuse solid waste through a circular economy, thereby helping preserve the natural environment.

2.3 The circular economy and sustainability.

Correal et al. (2023) state that the circular economy represents a great opportunity for solid waste management and sustainability. It is becoming increasingly important today as a new economic model that values human heritage. Instead of extracting new resources, this model reuses waste to rebuild products and extend their useful life.

The circular economy offers an alternative to the linear production-consumption model, which relies on extraction, production, use, and disposal. This linear process has led to the overexploitation of resources and accelerated waste generation, harming global sustainability and people alike.

Then, the proposed approach to solid waste management relies on three main principles. First, we must remember that natural resources are limited, so we need to use them efficiently and carefully. Second, it is important to distinguish waste from older production and consumption habits that follow a linear economy. Finally, this new economic model

helps us meet real human needs and, as a result, improves the quality of life for communities and their environments (Ordoñez and Pérez, 2026).

In summary, the circular economy relies on a systemic approach to production, using targeted strategies such as reduction, reuse, recycling, restoration, redesign, renovation, and reconstruction to extend the longevity of materials. This model supports the reconstruction of products, prolonging their utility and optimising use, while transforming waste into valuable resources and easing the strain on natural systems (Ogiemwonyi, 2025). Consequently, waste generation drops significantly, fostering ecosystem regeneration and reinforcing economic resilience, sustainability, and environmental stewardship.

2.4 University Social Responsibility.

The topic proposed here is the convergence of knowledge and practices that enable students to apply SRM directly to their professional training and ethical performance. This involves embracing environmental awareness and experiencing University Social Responsibility (USR), which transforms their worldview and turns them into strategic agents of social change.

Therefore, it is imperative that students consider their individual or collective contributions to environmental care as conscious decisions intended to address the environment's priority needs. However, to achieve this goal, it is necessary to promote the professional and research training of teachers and students, with the aim of developing specialised skills that enable the generation of efficient solutions that favour the care and preservation of the natural habitat.

This change will be effective as long as universities develop academic programmes with subjects that are properly aligned with the corresponding GRS in their curricula (Olivo et al., 2024). As Moreira (2025) has pointed out, this is reinforced by the significant percentage of students who do not properly classify such waste or practise its reuse. Likewise, limited sustainable practices and campaigns have been implemented that focus on operational waste management rather than on a conscious commitment to environmental care. For this reason, it is essential to strengthen three dimensions: knowledge, solid waste management capacity, and students' collaborative, creative, and innovative attitudes.

3 METHODOLOGY

To take advantage of the Sustainable Development course, which involves making proposals or actions for socio-environmental improvement, and to consider the advantages of solid waste for its management, a group of students used it to design and build a device or apparatus that would meet a specific need of vulnerable communities. It was therefore necessary to develop a work plan, which took the form of a manuscript structured as follows: proposal of ideas; selection and description of the selected idea; socio-environmental problem; justification; objectives; need it addresses; description of the construction process; results (involving the Sustainable Development Goals); conclusion (learning experience); and references, following the methodological line of Project-Based Learning (PBL) (Tapia et al., 2025; Medina et al., 2025) and certain elements for the design of a Technological Project (Morales et al., 2024; Elgezabal, 2015), given that the students were in the first semester of their degree programme.

The creative-innovative process.

The construction of the device had to follow a specific procedure requiring several aspects:

First, create a sketch/diagram: this is a drawing made with a programme (MatLab, Solidworks, LabVIEW, FreeCAD, etc.) that serves as a guide for the construction of the device.

Second, solid waste materials must be collected. To do this, those who are in optimal condition to meet the established objective must be selected and collected. It is essential that evidence of this action be presented.

Next, the materials must be sanitised by following these steps: first, the solid waste must be cleaned and dried. This step is vital, as it prevents harm to health. Subsequently, evidence corresponding to this part of the process will be presented.

Construction process: this involves integrating all the elements necessary to form the device or artefact. This process requires sub-phases to carry out functionality tests until the project's completion, providing evidence of the process.

Next, the device/artefact will be presented, and its functionality and operation explained.

Finally: delivery of the manuscript: upon completion of step five, the final document will be delivered in accordance with the stipulated characteristics. Standard language usage must be ensured. The specifications of the academic text, in accordance with APA format, seventh edition.

4. DEVELOPMENT AND CONSTRUCTION OF THE PROJECT PROCESS

One of the artefacts built by a group of students is presented, adding a description of the project developed by them in italics:

4.1 Name of the project.

Recycling and reuse of aluminium cans to create an electric grill.

4.2 Autores.

First-quarter term students in the Mechatronics programme:

Ávila Flores Jonathan Isaí.

Castillo Jiménez Edmundo.

Chávez Pérez Erick Joel.

Gallegos Castillo Miguel Ángel.

Garay Guardiola Álvaro Gadiel.

4.3 Issues.

At an international level, there has been an increase in global warming due to the pollution generated by aluminium cans, according to Carreño et al. (2024):

The extraction and processing of aluminium have a major environmental impact, including deforestation, water and air pollution, and waste generation. Furthermore, aluminium is a non-renewable resource. If waste is not reduced, reserves of this resource will be depleted more quickly, exacerbating environmental problems (p.6).

At the national level, pollution from aluminium cans both on land and at sea has a significant impact on the environment. According to Bautista (2010):

Its reactivity with other elements is high: when it comes into contact with oxygen, it undergoes a combustion reaction that generates a large amount of heat, and when combined with halogens and sulphur, it forms halides and sulphides. However, one of the greatest advantages of aluminium is that it can be recycled repeatedly without losing its quality or properties (p. 11).

Locally, in the Tampico-Madero-Altamira metropolitan area, there are serious pollution problems involving aluminium cans. According to Huerta (2023), 'discarded tyres, tree trunks and branches, dead animals, plastic containers and bags, PET bottles, aluminium cans, and even old household appliances have been removed from the city's drainage system' (para. 1), as they not only obstructed the urban flow of these, but also polluted and corrupted the environment.

4.5 Objective.

To create an aluminium electric grill that promotes the recycling of this solid waste material for domestic use, encourages its recycling and reconstruction, and provides an economical and efficient alternative for people who lack the budget to purchase it.

4.6 Justification.

Institutional:

This project is possible because the University is responsible for training professionals committed to comprehensive human development through cutting-edge educational processes that employ a competency-based approach, promoting science, technology, innovation, and academic excellence to impact the region's economic, environmental, social, and cultural development.

Academic:

This project is validated because it forms part of the Sustainable Development subject, which includes the creation and development of a sustainable project.

Social:

This work seeks to generate a positive impact on the community by promoting actions that contribute to social and environmental well-being, thereby encouraging a favourable change in people's quality of life.

4.7 Need it addresses.

Having a stove at home is a necessity, as cooking with firewood has a direct impact on nature. Unfortunately, not everyone has access to one, according to Lovera (2025), publishing in SEMMEXICO:

In 2023, the situation had hardly changed. Five specialists, three women and two men, confirmed that in Mexico, around 4.5 million households still use firewood for cooking for economic reasons, noting that firewood consumption in homes depends on factors such as cooking habits, gender differences, and oral tradition (para. 6).

In an interview conducted by Osornio (2025) with Don Rafael, a community leader with more than two decades of experience organising local projects, he pointed out: “people are hopeful, but there are also doubts. We want the stoves to be of good quality and properly installed. It is also important that we are taught how to use them correctly and how to maintain them” (para. 6).

Given that some parts of the population lack access to conventional household items or gas supply, this project aims to provide a sustainable, accessible alternative for low-income households through the design and construction of an electric grill made from recycled aluminium cans. The aim is to use reusable materials and improve the quality of life of people in vulnerable situations.

4.8 Steps for constructing the device.

The project began with the planning phase, in which the materials to be used and the nature of the work to be carried out were determined. As a result, it was decided to create an electric grill to address the lack of stoves in vulnerable communities.

To this end, the following was done:

4.8.1 *Collection of 0.25 mm aluminium cans (beer cans) and 0.2 mm aluminium cans; washing and disinfecting them.*

Image 1.

Collection of aluminium cans.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

A visit to Miramar Beach was made to collect the solid waste to be used to carry out the project idea.

4.8.2 *A sketch/drawing of the device was designed as a guide to bring the intended idea to life.*

Image 2.

Technical drawing of the prototype using FreeCAD.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

Several designs were developed for the grill to be built, opting for the one presented here to comply with the project outlined herein and meet the delivery time.

4.8.3 *The grill was measured at 55 cm long, 17 cm wide and 20 cm high.*

Image 3.

Grill measurements.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

Based on the sketch, a simulation was made of how the device should look before cutting the cans and assembling the parts that would make up the grill.

4.8.4 We began by cutting the cans according to the measurements previously established in the sketch.

Image 4.

Cutting cans.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

Cutting the cans required both precision and care, as it was possible to ruin the aluminium (wasting it) or cut one's fingers or hands. For this reason, more days were spent completing this phase of the project. In addition, a decision was made regarding the thickness of the cans to be used, opting for the thickest and most resistant cans to meet the intended objective.

4.8.5 *The cuts for the structure were assembled using Kolaloka glue and bicarbonate.*

Image 5.

Start of assembly

Source: own elaboration (2026).

Construction and assembly of the grill's base or casing began.

4.8.6 *Tins were used to construct the burners, choosing those that were thicker and more resistant.*

Image 6.

Construction of burners.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

A model of the device is presented; that is, a type of preliminary assembly to assess how to assemble the burners.

4.8.7 *Ground brick was used as insulation.*

Image 7.

Insulation.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

Ground refractory brick was used as an insulating material, incorporating it into the burners moulded from scrap cans.

4.8.8 *The internal parts of the grill were assembled/glued together using kolaloka and bicarbonate of soda.*

Image 8.

Assembly

Source: own elaboration (2026).

The height of the burners relative to the base of the casing was calculated, and measurements were taken to cut the sheet metal to the circumference of the burners.

4.8.9 Details of the casing were finalised.

Image 9.

Painting the casing.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

Details such as painting certain parts of the casing were finalised.

4.8.10 Assembly of the part and electrical connection..

Image 10.

Electrical connection.

Fuente: elaboración propia (2026).

The assembly was carried out from the inside outwards to connect the electrical part.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Results.

The developed and operating device was presented, in accordance with what the students proposed in their project, fulfilling the objectives established to achieve the intended goal, as well as meeting the requirement for its presentation at a local, regional, or national conference within a short time.

Imagen 11.

Grill finished.

Source: own elaboration (2026).

5.2 Student learning experience.

The creation of this grill enabled the management and recycling of solid waste, providing a viable alternative for reusing materials commonly thrown away and transforming them into a functional, useful domestic appliance for people with limited resources. It also provided an effective way to reuse aluminium cans, giving them a new, useful, and innovative purpose.

The construction process was carried out successfully, and the device met the set objective: the grill worked correctly, heating a container of water, demonstrating its functionality and efficiency.

The work carried out is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) established by the 2030 agenda (2026), with which the project is aligned:

SDG 7: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.

SDG 9: Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster innovation.

SDG 11: Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.

SDG 12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns, which are essential to sustaining the livelihoods of current and future generations.

SDG 13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.

5.3 Discussion.

According to Saltos et al. (2025), currently, the number of students who reuse solid materials (such as paper, packaging, and textiles) is low. This situation is attributed to the

limited adoption of circular economy strategies in universities. Furthermore, the lack of awareness-raising initiatives and the poor promotion of existing ones exacerbate this problem. As a result, peer waste reduction is minimal, and only a few teachers organise activities to sort and manage these materials. Therefore, it is necessary to implement an educational and participatory component that promotes sustainable behaviours and helps address the serious problem of environmental pollution.

In this regard, it is worth noting that the inclusion of subjects related to environmental protection and care in Mexican university curricula, established as a mandatory requirement, promotes practical and ethical-professional awareness among students, who are motivated to take actions that benefit society and the natural environment through WRS (Vian et al., 2025).

In the global context, there are renowned educational institutions that stand out for their exemplary waste management. These entities are located in countries with a high Human Development Index (HDI), where an optimal relationship between economic development and comprehensive waste management has been established (Vilchis et al., 2019).

Regarding this issue, a discrepancy has been observed in the positioning of Mexican higher education institutions in international rankings of developed countries. Khan (2025) reaffirms this argument, noting that, in the field of sustainability, the economic development of these nations is a relevant factor from a sociocultural perspective and significantly influences the efficiency of solid waste management practices.

On the other hand, proper management of natural resources, together with waste management such as recycling and reuse, and the application of technology (Di Foggia and Beccarello, 2021), can generate various social benefits, such as the creation of renewable energy sources for public lighting, the production of dishes made from fruit and vegetable peels by postgraduate students at the National Polytechnic Institute (IPN) (La Jornada, 2025), and edible packaging made from agricultural by-products (De Oliveira et al., 2025), among other achievements.

Consequently, the interrelationship between the circular economy and the environment, in the context of the current economic model, must fulfil three fundamental functions:

providing resources, assimilating waste and generating value. According to the Ecverde report (2021), there is an urgent need for durable products designed so they can be rebuilt and reincorporated as raw materials or useful tools for people in vulnerable situations.

Finally, the redesign of solid waste serves as a catalyst for cognitive and emotional processes among teachers and students through meticulous planning that incorporates pedagogical tools, particularly the integration of new specialised teaching methods. This approach is based on promoting comprehensive knowledge that favours sustainability (Pavón et al., 2024).

6 CONCLUSIONS

Certainly, solid waste management faces major challenges, such as the exponential increase in waste generation, limited landfill capacity, and negative environmental impacts. However, it is important to note that one alternative that mitigates this effect is education. It is an ideal means of combating this serious problem through awareness-raising, waste management, and the reuse and reconstruction of waste, driven by the creativity and innovation of young university students.

In this sense, sustainable development can be approached from a curricular perspective, in which the study plans and programmes (across various academic disciplines) of university institutions converge to produce graduates who are aware of their environment and sensitive to its needs, applying the knowledge they have acquired to shape their identity and professional work.

The importance of the circular economy for the use of solid waste is evident, as it ensures economic and social benefits, especially for vulnerable communities. The intention is to go beyond conventional educational spaces to make knowledge available to disadvantaged communities, address practical needs, and generate a metacognitive process that connects theory with human reality.

Therefore, it is imperative to promote activities that stimulate students' creative spirit, encouraging the incubation and generation of innovative ideas that help transform the current ecological and social environments of economically disadvantaged communities.

The project developed by the students highlights the relevance of the issue raised, as the proposal contributes to addressing, through GRS, one of the ecological problems affecting living beings today. However, a lack of interest in this reality will have significant negative consequences for the planet's sustainability.

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